

Multiscale modelling the effect of voids on short beam shear strength of composites

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Introduction

Voids are one of the most common manufacturing defects in composites. They can promote damage initiation at the micro-scale or meso-scale and affect the failure response of composite structures. Predicting the effects of voids on composite damage has long been sought for certification by analysis. Since full-scale models containing microscopic or mesoscopic void details are computationally prohibitive, the presented work focuses instead on employing multi-scale modelling approaches to investigate the effect of voids on the Short Beam Shear (SBS) strength of laminates.

Meso-scale RVE model

- Simulation steps under periodic boundary conditions:
- Step 1- Temperature drop for curing.
 - Step 2- In-plane shear.

High local residual stresses around voids at the end of thermal step.

Matrix-dominated damage is seen to initiate around voids in the 90° ply.

Macro-scale SBS model

- A 3D orthotropic material model is employed.
- Shear response is informed by the homogenized RVE model.
- Full 3D model of 3-point bending SBS setup.

Damage contours showing failure between rollers on the SBS model

Equivalent SBS strength $s_{13} = 80 \text{ MPa}$

Exploration

RVE models containing 1%-7% void volume fraction to take into account more void morphologies.

Macro-scale SBS models to represent meso-scale material behaviours. Effects of different combinations of void morphologies on the SBS strength of laminates are investigated.

Predicted SBS strengths and their correlation with existing experimental results[1]. Good agreement is shown between the linear fits.